

Evaluating common indicators of the effects of marine 1
protected areas on conservation and catches 2

3

33 **Introduction**

34 Various forms of spatial management have been used to conserve and manage marine ecosystems
35 across cultures throughout human history (e.g. Johannes 2002). The 1990s marked a period of
36 expanded interest in both the science and use of spatial management tools, specifically the general
37 concept of “marine protected areas” (MPAs) (Carr et al. 2019; Humphreys and Clark 2020). MPAs
38 are areas of the ocean where human activities are restricted or prohibited to promote biodiversity
39 conservation and potentially achieve other complementary objectives (Grorud-Colvert et al. 2021).
40 These objectives can include preserving cultural heritage, rebuilding populations inside protected
41 borders, providing conservation benefits outside in fished waters, and supporting surrounding
42 fisheries (Gaines et al. 2010). International movements such as the Montreal–Kunming Global
43 Biodiversity Framework’s call for protection of 30% of the oceans, and the Agreement under
44 the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the Conservation and Sustainable Use
45 of Marine Biological Diversity of Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (the High Seas Treaty or
46 BBNJ) have provided substantial momentum for the expanded use of MPAs in the world’s oceans
47 in pursuit of these goals.

48 Over 9% of the ocean is now covered by MPAs (as of October 2025; [World Database of Protected](#)
49 [Areas](#)), and the recent global expansion of MPAs has been matched by growing efforts to empir-
50 ically evaluate their performance (e.g. Osenberg et al. 2011; Edgar et al. 2014; Di Lorenzo et
51 al. 2020; Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez 2024; Hopf et al. 2024) . Since many of the benefits
52 that MPAs are expected to deliver are difficult to measure directly, evaluations of MPA effects
53 often rely on tracking simpler indicators as proxies for broader MPA effects (Pelletier 2011; Hopf
54 et al. 2024). These indicators enable assessments to be carried out across diverse contexts, and
55 have become a foundational tool for attempting to understand MPA effects in both scientific and
56 policy settings. Many indicators compare attributes within MPAs to nearby unprotected areas
57 (i.e., response ratios; Smith et al. (2024); Lester et al. (2009)), or from unprotected areas that are
58 near to MPA borders compared to those farther away (i.e., gradients, Halpern, Lester, and Kellner

2009). More causally-robust approaches incorporate measurements both before and after MPA implementation [i.e., before-after-control-impact or BACI; Medoff, Lynham, and Raynor (2022); Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez (2024); Kerr, Kritzer, and Cadrin (2019); Ovando et al. (2021)].

While these empirical indicators differ in their complexity, each is presumably intended to determine the effect of the MPA on a particular observed metric: higher biomass in MPAs compared to unprotected areas is interpreted as conservation gains within MPA borders (Smith et al. 2024; Lester et al. 2009), while gradients in fisheries catch or effort are thought to signal evidence of spillover of adult or larval fish from the MPA to surrounding waters (Halpern, Lester, and Kellner 2009; Medoff, Lynham, and Raynor 2022; Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez 2024; Roberts et al. 2001). However, these indicator results are sometimes then assumed to also imply evidence for an unobserved effect, such as changes in total population size or total fisheries catch.

The assumption that specific indicators can stand in for broader and harder to observe ecological or social effects has not been to our knowledge comprehensively tested, despite their widespread use (though works such as Hopf et al. (2024), Kerr, Kritzer, and Cadrin (2019), and Hilborn et al. (2024) evaluated specific combinations of indicators and effects). Understanding the reliability of indicators, and the variability of the underlying MPA effects they aim to measure, is critical for interpreting existing evaluations, designing effective monitoring strategies, and for evidence-based applied ecological decision-making.

This paper addresses two questions. We first analysed whether MPA effects on conservation and catches are likely to be variable enough to justify the need for empirical monitoring. We then tested the ability of several commonly used empirical indicators to reflect the actual effects of MPAs. We found that MPAs can have highly variable effects on conservation and catches depending on the specific social-ecological dynamics of the system in question, and that while some indicators reliably track this variability in some MPA effects, many do not.

83 **Materials and Methods**

84 **MPA Experiment Overview**

85 We used a simulation framework to model both the variability of MPA effects and the performance
86 of empirical MPA indicators within complex social–ecological systems. We simulated a fishery
87 system with a set of bio-economic traits. We then ran an MPA experiment on that system by
88 generating two paired simulations identical in every way, except that one system contained a
89 no-take MPA and the other did not. We then calculated the simulated effects of the MPA on a
90 range of objectives based on the differences between the simulation with an MPA relative to
91 the paired simulation without an MPA. Lastly, we calculated common empirical indicators of
92 MPA performance from the simulation with the MPA, and compared these indicators to the true
93 simulated effects. We then repeated this process multiple times with different randomly generated
94 fishery states. The details of this process are explained below and illustrated in Figure 1. See SI
95 and Figure S1 for a case study simulation of these processes.

96 **Simulating Fisheries**

97 Fisheries systems were simulated using the marlin model (Ovando et al. 2023; Ovando 2025).
98 marlin simulates a user-specified number of age-structured fish populations fished by a user-
99 specified number of fleets on a simulated seascape divided into “patches” of defined area. For this
100 paper, we modeled a 21 by 21 grid of patches (441 total), each 25 km² (5 km × 5 km), for a total
101 seascape area of 11,025 km².

102 To explore MPA effects and indicators across a range of species, we modeled four species
103 archetypes defined by fixed and variable parameters, broadly based on a tuna (*Thunnus albacares*),
104 shark (*Carcharhinus falciformis*), grouper (*Epinephelus fuscoguttatus*), and reef fish (*Seriola*
105 *quinqueradiata*). Fixed parameters included growth, mortality, fecundity, recruitment, and move-
106 ment, with values based on the literature and our judgement (Table S1). We fixed these to avoid

Figure 1: Conceptual illustration of the process of simulating effects of MPAs, calculating empirical indicators, and comparing indicators to effects. Colored polygons in Step 2 indicate habitat distributions for each simulated species. See Methods section for detailed explanations of these steps.

107 unrealistic combinations of, for example, growth and mortality (Prince et al. 2015). Each iteration
108 of the model also used draws from a list of variable parameters (Table S2).

109 The model simulates movement across the two-dimensional seascape through passive diffusion
110 and active taxis along habitat gradients, following J. T. Thorson et al. (2021) and Ovando (2025).
111 Movement rates of recruits and post-recruits were set so that 95% of individuals remained within
112 a given linear distance of their origin after one year. These distances were grouped into low (2.5
113 km), medium (25 km), or high (250 km) dispersal and assigned to recruit and post-recruit stages to
114 reflect a range of movement dynamics (e.g. sedentary adults and highly dispersed larvae, and *vice*
115 *versa*; Table S1). These values are not intended as true movement rates for the named species.

116 For each simulation we augmented fixed parameters with random draws of variable parameters de-
117 scribing less-certain aspects of the system (Table S2). Ecological traits included the uniformity of
118 species-level habitat, the correlation in habitat across species, seasonal movement shifts, spawning
119 aggregations, the timing and strength of density dependence, and the magnitude and correlation
120 structure of recruitment deviation (Table S2). Variable traits also included fishery characteristics
121 such as fishing pressure on each species, species- and fleet-specific economic value, the presence
122 of ports that affect spatial choices, and fleet selectivity (Table S2).

123 Fish populations can be heterogeneously distributed in space, and species distributions can exhibit
124 positive, negative, or no correlations with other fished species (J. T. Thorson and Barnett 2017;
125 Karp et al. 2025; Brodie et al. 2021; Lopez et al. 2024). Following Ovando et al. (2023) and
126 Ovando (2025), for each species we randomly set a parameter κ describing habitat heterogeneity:
127 lower κ yields smoother habitat and higher κ yields more patchy habitat. We also generated a
128 habitat correlation matrix among species. These κ values and the correlation matrix were used to
129 construct a covariance matrix for a multivariate normal distribution, from which we drew spatial
130 habitat fields. These draws produce species distributions that vary across simulations in both their
131 heterogeneity and cross-species correlation.

132 Our model also accounts for some of the complex behaviors of fishing fleets. Fleets can adapt

their spatial and temporal distribution in response to fishing opportunities and regulations. The simulated effects of an MPA are sensitive to whether fishers adjust to new regulations, for example by concentrating effort along MPA borders, which can strongly influence outcomes (Ovando 2025).

We allowed for different effort dynamics. For any given fleet in a simulation, total fishing effort across patches was based on a random selection of either *Constant Effort* or *Open Access*. Under *Constant Effort*, total effort is fixed over time unless a policy such as an MPA is implemented. Under *Open Access*, total effort can expand or contract from year to year based on prior profitability and under stable conditions evolves towards a bionomic equilibrium with zero profits (Costello et al. 2016; Cabral et al. 2019).

Given total effort, fleets allocate effort across patches based on either profits or revenue, randomly chosen for each fleet. When dynamics are profit-based, costs can increase with distance from the fleet's home port. MPA implementation can cause effort to redistribute or leave the fishery. Under displacement, effort that was inside the MPA is reallocated to patches outside in the time step following implementation, according to the fleet's spatial rule. Under effort attrition, effort that was inside the MPA exits the fishery. Under *Open Access*, total effort can subsequently adjust over time. Together, these dynamics allow fleets to adjust both the total amount of effort and its spatial distribution in response to opportunities and MPAs.

All else being equal, MPAs have greater effects in heavily fished systems than in lightly fished ones (Hilborn et al. 2004). We simulated fishing pressure by randomly selecting a baseline fishing mortality rate for each species, held constant in the absence of an MPA. Because the same fishing mortality can have different effects depending on life history and selectivity, we summarize fishing pressure using baseline "depletion", measured as pre-MPA biomass (B) divided by unfished biomass (B_0), B/B_0 . Values near zero indicate heavily fished populations, and values near one indicate lightly fished populations. The distribution of baseline B/B_0 across simulations is shown in Figure S25.

159 The four species archetypes were used in three bio-economic fishery systems of increasing com-
160 plexity. The *simple* scenario is single-species, single-fleet, matching the most common way of
161 modeling MPA effects on one population and one fleet. The *medium* scenario is multi-species,
162 single-fleet, with all four species in the same seascape, allowing positively or negatively correlated
163 spatial distributions and variable vulnerability. The *complex* scenario is multi-species, multi-fleet,
164 with two fleets that differ in selectivity and fishing pressure, allowing dynamics such as a species
165 being targeted by one fleet and taken as bycatch by another.

166 In total, each simulated fishery is built from combinations of fixed and variable bio-economic
167 parameters (Table S1; Table S2) and the chosen complexity level. We projected each fishery for 75
168 years to approximate pre-MPA equilibrium conditions.

169 **Simulating MPA Effects**

170 We ran each simulated fishery through an MPA experiment where all attributes of the simulated
171 fishery were held at identical values, except for the application of an MPA. Our MPA experiments
172 were created from a factorial combination of MPA size (represented as the percent of the surface
173 area of the seascape covered in a fully protected – i.e., no-take – MPA) and the placement strategy
174 of the MPA (*Avoid Fishing* or *Target Fishing*). MPA size ranged from 5% to 60% of the seascape,
175 in increments of 5%. Under the *Target Fishing* strategy, patches are placed in an MPA in descend-
176 ing order of total biomass caught, under the *Avoid Fishing* strategy, patches are placed in an MPA
177 in ascending order of total biomass caught.

178 We also explored how effects varied depending on whether the MPAs were individual entities
179 (*contiguous*) or divided across a network (*mosaic*) (Gaines et al. 2010; Pons et al. 2022). However,
180 all results presented here used the *mosaic* strategy since we tested the sensitivity of our results
181 to using *contiguous* MPAs and found no it had no meaningful impacts, so omitted those runs to
182 reduce computational overhead.

183 After running each fishery for 75 years to reach equilibrium conditions, we then ran each fishery

through each MPA scenario for 20 more years. 20 years was selected to give enough time for MPA effects to develop, without necessarily guaranteeing equilibrium conditions, reflecting the reality of real-world MPA monitoring programs. Running the models for more years had no meaningful effect on our results. After 20 years, we calculated the following MPA effects:

- Total biomass per species inside MPA borders (*Biomass Inside*)
- Total biomass per species outside MPA borders (*Biomass Outside*)
- Total biomass per species (*Total Biomass*)
- Total catch per species and fleet (*Catch*)

The true effects of the MPAs on each of these metrics was calculated by comparing the percentage difference in the relevant values after 20 years post burn-in in the simulation with the MPA relative to the paired simulation without the MPA. An MPA effect value of 20% means that the metric in question was 20% higher in the simulation with the MPA than the same metric in the paired simulation without the MPA.

Filtering Simulations

While we took steps to restrict the simulations to realistic scenarios (e.g. fixing core life history traits), some combinations of parameters still produced implausible results, which were removed from the final analysis. We removed simulations in which any species had extremely low baseline depletion levels (less than 1% of unfished biomass), as while not impossible such extreme levels of depletion are rare in marine fish populations and produce extreme results when considering MPA effects on a percentage based scale. We removed any simulations in which any species had total biomass values less than one, or any fishing fleet had catches less than one. These simulations were removed since they resulted in improbably high percentage effect sizes. Post-filtering, the combination of each simulated fishery with each MPA design resulted in a total of 10,896 unique MPA experiments.

208 **Calculating Empirical Indicators**

209 The prior steps of simulating a fishery system under a range of MPA experiments create a distri-
210 bution of causal effects of MPAs on the selected metrics. We compared these true effects with
211 estimates from common empirical indicators of MPA performance. To isolate the fundamental
212 performance of the indicator from questions around data quality and bias, all indicators were
213 calculated using the simulated data without any observation error.

214 We evaluated six empirical indicators commonly used to assess MPA performance; *Biomass*
215 *Density Before-After-Control-Impact* (BACI), *Biomass Density Response Ratio*, *Mean Length*
216 *Response Ratio*, *Effort Gradient*, *Biomass Density Gradient*, *Biomass Density Before-After Gradi-*
217 *ent* (Table 1). These indicators vary in their underlying response variable (biomass density, mean
218 length, or fishing effort), their spatial design (*inside-outside* or *near-far*), and whether they include
219 temporal comparisons (*before-after* vs. *after-only*). These indicators were selected to represent a
220 range of approaches described in the empirical MPA literature to infer conservation and fisheries
221 effects. A full description of each indicator and its stylized equation is provided in Table 1.

222 All models were fit using a log-normal distribution, with the dependent variable measured at the
223 resolution of species, patch, and time step (and by fleet where applicable). Coefficients from these
224 models can be interpreted as multiplicative effects; effect sizes are reported as percentage changes
225 using the transformation $100 \times (e^{\beta_{MPA}} - 1)$. All indicators were calculated at the species level,
226 as results were robust to aggregating biomass or catch across species (Figure S30).

227 Indicators based on *inside-outside* comparisons (e.g., Biomass Response Ratio, Biomass BACI,
228 Mean Length Response Ratio) require the selection of a comparable reference site outside the
229 MPA. In empirical studies, reference sites are often selected to match the habitat and environ-
230 mental characteristics within the MPA (Chapman and Kramer 1999; Claudet and Guidetti 2010;
231 Osenberg et al. 2011; Smith et al. 2024). We approximated this reference site selection approach
232 by controlling for unfished biomass per patch and weighting regressions by distance from the MPA
233 border.

Gradient (*near-far*) indicators (e.g., Effort Gradient, Biomass Gradient, Biomass Before-After Gradient) compare metrics outside of MPAs based on distance from MPA borders. Following the general approach of Medoff, Lynham, and Raynor (2022) and Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez (2024), we calculated the linear distance from each patch from the MPA border, and assigned patches in the lowest 20th percentile of distance as *Near* and those in the top 80th percentile as *Far*. As with *inside-outside* style analyses, we also controlled for unfished biomass per species per patch.

All models were fit using linear models in R (R Core Team 2024). For each indicator, variables were measured without error at the resolution of spatial patch p and time step t . The spatial resolution of the system is 21 by 21 patches, meaning that any given time step has 441 patches. For models fit to a single time step then (e.g. *Biomass Density Response Ratio*), the number of data points used to fit the model were $N = 441$. For models fit to multiple time steps of before and after, (e.g. *Biomass Density BACI*), the number of data points used to fit the model were $N = 882$.

Table 1: General structure of tested MPA indicators. Bolded β denotes the estimated MPA effect. B = biomass; E = effort; ML = mean length. INSIDE/OUTSIDE indicate patches inside or outside MPA borders; BEFORE/AFTER indicate time relative to implementation; NEAR/FAR refer to proximity to the MPA border. All models include covariates for unfished biomass and distance weighting (omitted here for clarity). Indicators without a time term are measured in the final simulation year (20 years post-implementation).

Indicator	Estimated Effect and Key Assumptions	Example Use	Equation
Biomass Density Before-After -Control-Impact (<i>inside-outside</i>)	Ratio of change in B after MPA implementation inside MPA relative to outside MPA. Assumes Parallel trends in B inside and outside MPA pre- and post-implementation.	Hopf et al. (2024)	$\log(B_{p,t}) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 INSIDE_p + \beta_2 AFTER_t + \beta_3 INSIDE_p \times AFTER_t$

Indicator	Estimated Effect and Key Assumptions	Example Use	Equation
Biomass Density Response Ratio (<i>inside-outside</i>)	Post-MPA Ratio of B inside MPA relative to outside MPA. Assumes no pre-existing differences in B between inside and outside sites	Smith et al. (2024)	$\log(B_p) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 INSIDE_p$
Mean Length Response Ratio (<i>inside-outside</i>)	Post-MPA ratio of ML inside MPA relative to outside MPA. Assumes no pre-existing differences in ML between inside and outside patches.	Halpern (2003)	$\log(ML_p) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 INSIDE_p$
Effort Gradient (<i>near-far</i>)	Post-MPA ratio of E near MPA relative to far. Assumes no pre-existing differences in E between near and far patches.	Goni et al. (2008)	$\log(E_p) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 NEAR_p$
Biomass Density Gradient (<i>near-far</i>)	Post-MPA ratio of B near MPA relative to far from MPA. Assumes no pre-existing differences in B between near and far patches.	Halpern, Lester, and Kellner (2009)	$\log(B_p) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 NEAR_p$
Biomass Density Before-After Gradient (<i>near-far</i>)	Ratio of change in B after MPA implementation near to MPA relative to far from MPA. Assumes Parallel trends in B density near and far from MPA pre- and post-implementation.	Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez (2024)	$\log(B_{p,t}) \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 NEAR_p + \beta_2 AFTER_t + \beta_3 NEAR_p \times AFTER_t$

247 We do not report uncertainty of estimates, as our primary objective is to evaluate relative perfor-
248 mance across indicators rather than to make statistical inference. Given that this is a simulation-
249 based analysis with arbitrarily defined sample sizes, conventional statistical significance testing is
250 not meaningful (White et al. 2014), so we do not evaluate indicators against statistical significance
251 thresholds (e.g., $p < 0.05$). Similarly, we do not account for statistical complexities such as spatio-
252 temporal clustering (J. T. Thorson and Kristensen 2024) or zero-inflation (Zuur 2009). Applied use
253 of empirical indicators would need to be tailored to the local context, following best practices in
254 modeling and causal inference based on observational data from social-ecological systems.

California Response Ratio Case Study

255

We created a subset of our simulations selected to match the estimated response ratios from a network of MPAs along the coast of California, USA, reported in Smith et al. (2024). These response ratios are reported at the level of individual MPAs, with separate ratios for the total biomass density of targeted and non-targeted fishes. In order to match these empirical response ratios, we sampled 2500 of our MPA experiments with replacement using a weighting scheme designed to produce a distribution of *Biomass Density Response Ratios* that matched those reported in Smith et al. (2024) (see Figure S27). We restricted the candidate simulations for this process to MPA sizes between 10% and 40%, and to *medium* and *complex* levels of complexity, to more closely reflect plausible scenarios for the California system. This allowed us to examine what range simulated MPA effects could be associated with the distribution of *Biomass Density Response Ratios* measured in the California MPAs studied in Smith et al. (2024). Note that we do not claim these as being simulations of the California MPA system itself, but rather a set of simulations constrained to match a distribution of *Biomass Density Response Ratios* seen in a real-world system.

Comparing MPA Effects and Indicators

269

We assessed the ability of each indicator to track each outcome using a range of metrics. We measured the correlation between each indicator and each outcome using Spearman's rank correlations (ρ), given the potential for highly different scales between the indicator and the effects and the potential for non-linear relationships between the indicator and the effects. We converted these ρ values into ρ^2 values that reflect the proportion of the rank-order variance in the outcome that is explained by the indicator. These Spearman's rank correlation values provide a general sense of the extent to which a higher indicator value in one MPA experiment and a lower indicator value in another MPA experiment corresponds to a relatively higher outcome value at the first MPA experiment and a relatively lower outcome value at the second MPA experiment.

To assess how accurately each indicator reflected the true outcome, we calculated the root mean

280 squared error (RMSE) and the mean error (Bias) for each indicator-outcome pair. These metrics
281 are expressed in percentage points, not percent differences. For example, a Bias of -20 means
282 that the indicator underestimated the true outcome by an average of 20 percentage points (e.g.,
283 estimating 30% when the true value is 50%), not that it was 20% lower. Similarly an RMSE of 20
284 percentage points indicates typical deviations of about +/- 20 percentage points, not that the error
285 was within 20% of the true outcome.

286 **Reproducing Results**

287 All code needed to fully reproduce the results and manuscript are publicly available at
288 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17308920>.

289 **Results**

290 **Variability of MPA Effects**

291 Our simulated fisheries varied in their behavior as a function of the fixed (Table S1) and variable
292 (Table S2) simulation parameters. The degree of resulting fishing pressure, and subsequent deple-
293 tion, is one of the most important determinants of MPA effects. The median depletion (B/B_0)
294 value across all our included simulations was 0.38, mean value 0.41, ranging from a minimum of
295 0.01 and a maximum of 1.29 (noting that values above 1 are possible given recruitment variation).

296 Our simulated MPAs had a wide range of effects on species-level biomass and catch, with both
297 positive and negative causal effects possible for all measured effects (Figure 2). Increasing MPA
298 size generally expanded the range of possible effects. MPAs caused an increase in *Biomass*
299 *Inside* their borders in nearly all simulations (96%), though negative effects were also observed
300 in 4%. In contrast, *Biomass Outside* MPA borders increased in 48% of simulations, indicating a
301 roughly even likelihood of positive or negative effects on biomass beyond MPA borders across our
302 simulations. This asymmetry resulted in a net increase in *Total Biomass* in 88% of simulations and

a net decrease in 12% of simulations. Negative MPA effects for *Biomass Inside* and *Total Biomass* 303
were more common when the MPA placement strategy was to avoid fishing and when fishing 304
effort was displaced by the MPA, as these scenarios generally resulted in the concentration of 305
fishing effort in prime habitat. The possibility of the MPA causing net losses in biomass increased 306
with the level of fishing pressure (Figure 2). 307

MPAs resulted in a net increase in species- and fleet-level *Catch* in 27% of simulations, and a 308
net decrease in *Catch* in 73% of simulations. Smaller effect sizes on *Catch* (absolute effect sizes 309
less than 25%) were much more common than larger effect sizes. Using the *Avoid Fishing* MPA 310
strategy resulted in slightly lower frequency of net catch losses than the *Target Fishing* strategy, 311
but only slightly less so. While negative catch effects still occurred across all simulated levels 312
of fishing pressure, the number of simulations with positive catch effects increased with the 313
counterfactual degree of fishing pressure (Figure 2). 314

Figure 2: Distribution of simulation results across MPA effects (panels), proportion of seascape in MPA (columns), and level of baseline depletion in the absence of MPAs (colors, biomass B divided by unfished biomass B_0). Y-axis shows the “MPA effect”, the percent change in the outcome in question caused by the MPA. *Biomass Inside* refers to total individual species biomass inside MPA borders. *Biomass Outside* refers to total individual species biomass outside MPA borders. *Total Biomass* refers to total individual species biomass both inside and outside MPA borders. *Catch* refers to total catch per species and fleet outside the MPA.

Performance of Empirical Indicators of MPA Effects

315

The ability of empirical indicators to track MPA effects varied widely (Figure 3 A). All three *inside-outside* indicators had positive Spearman's ρ with *Biomass Inside* and *Total Biomass*, with *Biomass Density BACI* having the highest ρ values for both ($\rho = 0.64$ and $\rho = 0.45$ respectively), followed by *Biomass Density Response Ratio* ($\rho = 0.56$ and $\rho = 0.38$ respectively). All three *inside-outside* indicators had negative Spearman's ρ values with *Biomass Outside*, meaning that simulations with relatively higher biomass density response ratios were associated with simulations with relatively lower *Biomass Outside* effects.

Gradient indicators exploiting *near-far* patterns around MPAs had much lower Spearman's ρ values across all effects (all $|\rho| \leq 0.2$), explaining almost none of the rank-level variation in any of the evaluated MPA effects. Among the *near-far* indicators, *Effort Gradients* had the highest correlation values, ($\rho = 0.2$ for *Biomass Inside* and $\rho = 0.16$ for *Total Biomass*) (Figure 3).

None of the evaluated indicators were meaningfully correlated with the effects of MPAs on total catches, though all estimated correlations were negative. *Biomass Density BACI* had the clearest negative correlation with MPA effects on catch, with $\rho = -0.14$ (Figure 3).

The ρ values shown in Figure 3 indicate correlation between the indicator value and the outcome value. These correlations tell us how reliably an indicator can be used to rank different MPAs in terms of performance related to a specific MPA effect. We also examined how well raw indicator values represented raw MPA effects by calculating measures of error (root mean squared error) and bias (mean absolute error), where positive bias values indicate that, on average, indicator values were higher than true values, and *vice versa*. These metrics are more useful for determining how well the value of a given indicator at one MPA translates into the value of a given effects at the same MPA. The average RMSE across all indicators was 93 percentage points, with an average bias across all indicators of 13 percentage points. Most indicators were positively biased relative to the true effect size, though some indicators were negatively biased for *Biomass Inside* and *Total Biomass*.

341 All of the results shown in Figure 3 are based comparisons at the level of individual species and
342 where applicable fleets, for example comparing the *Biomass Density BACI* value for reef fish
343 to the true effect of the MPA on reef fish catches by an individual fleet. We also ran our results
344 on total values, comparing for example the *Biomass Density BACI* value aggregated across all
345 simulated species to the true effect of the MPA on all catches across all fleets (Figure S31). Doing
346 so had no substantial impact on the core results presented in the body of the paper.

Figure 3: Spearman correlations ρ (A) and ρ^2 (B) between indicators (y-axis) and MPA effects (x-axis) at the level of individual species and fleets across all simulations. Root mean squared error (RMSE, C) and mean error (Bias, D) between indicators (y-axis) and effects (x-axis) at the level of individual species and fleets across all simulations. Plain text y-axis labels indicates *inside-outside* indicators, *italic* y-axis labels indicate a *near-far* indicator. Text shows the value of the metric in question, also reflected in the background color of each cell according to the associated colorbar legend.

347 California Response Ratio Case Study

348 Sub-setting our results to only *Biomass Density Response Ratio* values that match the distribution
349 of response ratios for targeted species reported in Smith et al. (2024) allows us to visualize the
350 concepts shown in Figure 3. Simulated response ratios were positively correlated with *Biomass*
351 *Inside* and *Total Biomass* ($\rho = 0.48$, $\rho = 0.37$), and negatively correlated with *Biomass Outside*
352 and *Catch* ($\rho = -0.28$, $\rho = -0.1$) (Figure 4).

353 While *Biomass Density Response Ratios* had a high ρ value with *Biomass Inside*, there was sub-
354 stantial variation in this relationship, with low *Biomass Density Response Ratios* in fact being
355 associated with large changes in *Biomass Inside*, and *vice versa*. This was amplified for relation-
356 ships with lower correlations, such as *Biomass Density Response Ratios* and *Catch*, in which
357 *Biomass Density Response Ratios* of 0.5 could be produced by simulations with up to 100% in-
358 creases in catch or 100% losses in catch, or commonly with no meaningful change in catch at all
359 (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Simulated Biomass Density Response Ratios (x-axis) plotted against simulated MPA effects (y-axis), with distribution of response ratios matched to empirical response ratios of targeted finfish reported by Smith et al. (2024). Constrained to MPA sizes between 10-40% of seascape and the scenarios with multiple co-existing species. Text shows Spearman ρ correlations and ρ^2 values.

360 **Discussion**

361 Our results show that MPA effects on conservation and catches can be highly variable in both
362 magnitude and direction, underscoring the need for monitoring and evaluating MPAs rather than
363 assuming their effects *a priori*.

364 **Variability of MPA Effects**

365 MPAs almost always increased *Biomass Inside* their borders (96% of simulations), though the
366 magnitude of these gains varied depending on variables such as MPA size, placement, and fishing
367 pressure. However, we also found that *Biomass Outside* the MPA declined in 52% of our simula-
368 tions, indicating that spillover from inside MPAs was often insufficient to overcome the effects
369 of concentrated fishing effort outside. Overall, increases in *Biomass Inside* MPAs were typically
370 large enough that *Total Biomass* (inside and outside) still increased in 88% of simulations, despite
371 potential reductions in *Biomass Outside*.

372 Our result that MPAs can reduce total biomass is perhaps unintuitive. Consider a scenario where
373 an MPA is placed on the core habitat of one species, but in doing so displaces fishing effort onto
374 the core habitat of another species. This displacement can result in a net increase in the total
375 fishing mortality on this second species, and a subsequent decline in total biomass. While these
376 negative effects on total biomass were relatively rare (12% of simulations), our findings highlight
377 the potential for unintended consequences of MPAs, particularly when fished species and fishing
378 fleets have heterogeneous distributions and behaviors Pons et al. (2022).

379 While MPAs caused a net increase in *Total Biomass* in 88% of simulations, and a net increase in
380 *Biomass Outside* the MPA in 48% of simulations, MPAs reduced *Catch* in 73% of simulations.
381 This shows that in the majority of our simulations, MPAs caused a trade-off of better conservation
382 but lower catches. This trade-off was not due to a lack of spillover effects in our simulations, but
383 rather that in those simulations the amount of spillover from the MPA was not sufficient to make
384 up for the loss in fishing grounds caused by the protected area.

However, our results also confirm that MPAs can produce win-win outcomes where biomass and catch both increase (21% of simulations) more commonly when the fish population in question would have been highly overfished in the absence of an MPA (35% of simulations where $B/B_0 \leq 0.25$), and the MPA size was not too large relative to the movement dynamics of the fished species (or too small to have a meaningful effect) (Figure S29). Under these win-win conditions, the spillover benefits of the MPA rebuilding an overfished population were sufficient to overcome to loss in fishing grounds.

All else being equal MPAs had greater positive conservation effects in simulations with larger MPAs and more overfished (lower B/B_0) populations, and more negative catch effects in larger MPAs and less heavily fished (higher B/B_0) populations (Figure 2). However, these variables only explained part of the distribution of MPA effects, with MPAs of the same size protecting equally fished populations producing vastly different effects on conservation and catches depending on other state variables (Table S1; Table S2). Collectively, our results demonstrate that the effects of MPAs on conservation and catches are a complex function of many interacting bio-economic variables including MPA size, fish movement across different life stages, fishing pressure, and the responses of fishing fleets to spatial closures.

Performance of MPA Indicators

Our findings complement past studies noting that common MPA indicators can perform well but can also be misleading when faced the complex dynamics of marine social-ecological systems (Hopf et al. 2024; Kerr, Kritzer, and Cadrin 2019; Hilborn et al. 2024; Claudet and Guidetti 2010; Ferraro, Sanchirico, and Smith 2018; Christie et al. 2019). We extend this literature by providing a comprehensive evaluation of the performance of multiple indicators as proxies for a range of MPA effects under a wide set of bio-economic states.

The most reliable combination of indicators and effects were *inside-outside* indicators such as *Biomass Density BACI* and *Response Ratios* as proxies for biomass effects of MPAs, with the

410 strongest correlations with *Biomass Inside*. Numerous studies have pointed out that *inside-outside*
411 indicators are likely to provide biased estimates of the conservation effects of MPAs given uncon-
412 trolled for violations to the core assumptions of these indicators such as differences in baseline
413 habitat inside versus outside, recruitment shocks, biological spillover, and fishing fleet responses,
414 are common in marine social-ecological systems (Ferraro, Sanchirico, and Smith 2018; Larsen,
415 Meng, and Kendall 2019; Hilborn et al. 2022; Ovando et al. 2021; Hopf et al. 2024). Our results
416 show that even when faced with these biasing factors, *inside-outside* indicators still could be rea-
417 sonably reliable proxies for the relative conservation performance of different MPAs, as evidenced
418 by the relatively high Spearman’s ρ values (Figure 3). However, these *inside-outside* indicators
419 were still generally imprecise (high RMSE) and biased, indicating that one cannot reliably in-
420 terpret the specific values of an *inside-outside* indicator as the numerical effect on an MPA on
421 conservation.

422 None of indicators evaluated in this study reliably tracked the effects of MPAs on fishery catches
423 (Figure 3). This highlights an urgent need for research on effective indicators of the effects of
424 MPAs on fishery catches, as our simulation results indicate that negative effects can be common.
425 Collection of actual data on the economic performance of fisheries (rather than indirect indicators
426 such as spillover gradients) could help provide better estimates of catch effects, though finding suit-
427 able “control” fisheries to isolate the causal effect of MPAs on total catch from other exogenous
428 shocks (e.g. changes in fuel prices or market demand) will be difficult.

429 *Near-far* indicators exploiting gradients outside of MPAs methods have a long history in MPA
430 science (Halpern, Lester, and Kellner 2009; Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez 2024; Medoff, Lyn-
431 ham, and Raynor 2022; Roberts et al. 2001; Di Lorenzo, Claudet, and Guidetti 2016; Methratta
432 2020). However, *Near-far* indicators failed to track any simulated MPA effect, despite our model
433 producing strong gradients in simulated biomass and effort (Figure S28). Both simulation model-
434 ing and empirical evidence have confirmed that some level of spillover will almost always occur
435 at one or more life stages given the movement dynamics of marine organisms (Cudney-Bueno

et al. 2009; Di Lorenzo et al. 2020; Franceschini, Lynham, and Madin 2024; Gaines et al. 2010; 436
Hilborn et al. 2004; Hilborn et al. 2024). The more relevant question is what does observing a 437
spillover gradient tell us? Our results show that under our simulated conditions, the presence of 438
true spillover gradients in for example biomass density or fishing effort caused by an MPA, is not 439
generally necessary nor sufficient evidence for the effects of MPAs on *Biomass Inside*, *Biomass* 440
Outside, *Total Biomass*, or *Catch*. 441

Ensembles of *near-far* indicators might perform better than any individual one (Anderson et al. 442
2017). There are also other potential objectives of MPAs that may perhaps be reliably tracked 443
by gradient-based methods. For example, increases in the size and abundance of fish near MPA 444
borders may be of high value to recreational fishers (Franceschini, Lynham, and Madin 2024), 445
even if those increases on the border do not necessarily equate to commensurate benefits at the 446
scale of the total population or fishery. 447

The poor performance of *near-far* indicators as proxies for broader MPA effects in our model 448
presents a major challenge for evaluating MPAs where only fishery-dependent data from outside 449
MPAs are available. Evaluations of large high-seas MPAs created through efforts such as BBNJ 450
are likely to depend solely on fisheries data from outside the MPA (Medoff, Lynham, and Raynor 451
2022; Lynham and Villaseñor-Derbez 2024), as the costs to conduct fishery-independent surveys in 452
large and remote pelagic MPAs are likely to be prohibitive. Hampton et al. (2023) provides a good 453
example of integration of fishery-dependent data with process-based models to estimate the effects 454
of high-seas MPAs on tuna fisheries. Novel sources of data such as the acoustic signals collected 455
by Fish Aggregating Devices used in tuna fisheries could also be explored (Moreno et al. 2019). 456

It is important to note that even among the indicators with relatively higher correlations (*inside-* 457
outside), the sign of the correlation coefficient was not consistent. To illustrate, *Biomass Density* 458
Response Ratios observed in targeted fish species around California MPAs were generally pos- 459
itive, often substantially so (Smith et al. 2024). Our simulation results show that while higher 460
response ratios were generally produced by better *Biomass Inside* outcomes, higher *Biomass* 461

462 *Density Response Ratios* were associated with relatively worse *Biomass Outside* and *Catch* effects
463 (Figure 4).

464 We concur with Hopf et al. (2024) that while purely empirical methods have value, efforts to esti-
465 mate the effects of MPAs should ideally be placed in the context of the complexities and dynamics
466 of marine social-ecological systems. Bayesian estimation techniques provide a natural means for
467 encoding prior information based on other studies or bio-economic theory. Use of spatio-temporal
468 modeling to appropriately standardize spatial observations (J. T. Thorson 2019) so that they can
469 be passed to or integrated into spatial stock assessments (Punt 2019) could provide statistically
470 rigorous estimates of changes in fishing mortality rates and biomass relative to reference points as
471 a function fo MPA implementation, though these methods are highly data- and expertise-intensive.

472 **Caveats**

473 The model omits ecological processes such as trophic interactions and temporal trends in habitat
474 or life history, which are likely to become increasingly important under climate change (Fredston-
475 Hermann et al. 2020). We also evaluated only a subset of possible MPA effects and their interac-
476 tions, omitting objectives such as fishery profitability that are more challenging to model but could
477 alter welfare outcomes—for example, cases where reduced catch is offset by tourism benefits (Ban
478 et al. 2019).

479 MPA indicators and effects both evolve over time (Hopf et al. 2024; Ovando, Dougherty, and Wil-
480 son 2016; Nickols et al. 2019); future work could examine how sampling windows and observation
481 error influence results. We assumed that MPAs are fully no-take and perfectly enforced; relaxing
482 either assumption would further complicate studies of MPA effects (Claudet and Guidetti 2010).

483 Empirical evaluations of MPA effects should follow good practices in causal inference in spatial
484 social-ecological systems; see Ferraro, Sanchirico, and Smith (2018), McElreath (2020), Zuur
485 (2009), Byrnes and Dee (2025), Punt (2019), J. Thorson and Kristensen (2024), Tredennick et al.
486 (2021), Grace (2024), White et al. (2011), Hopf et al. (2024), Hilborn et al. (2022), and Ovando et

al. (2021) for guidance.

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Conclusions

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The use of MPAs is likely to expand rapidly in both coastal seas and the open ocean. Our simulations support the expectation that MPAs generally increase biomass inside their borders and at the total population level, although the magnitude of these gains is highly uncertain. In contrast, effects outside MPA borders on both biomass and catch are far less predictable and may be highly positive, highly negative, or anywhere in between, with negative catch effects more common in our simulations.

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It is therefore important to quantify the costs and benefits produced by MPAs and update our understanding of effective design and use of MPAs as new evidence accumulates, focusing on outcomes achieved rather than area protected. Our results provide practical guidance for interpreting widely used indicators, helping bridge ecological theory, applied monitoring, and management decisions. We show that while imperfect, some empirical indicators—particularly inside–outside indicators such as response ratios—can be reasonably reliable indicators of conservation outcomes inside MPAs. However, few commonly used empirical indicators reliably track effects outside MPAs, especially on fishery catches, and gradient-based near–far methods performed particularly poorly for any effect evaluated here.

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The next generation of MPA research needs interdisciplinary collaborations to develop sufficiently reliable and practical methods for tracking MPA effects. Doing so will help ensure that future expansion of protected areas in the world’s oceans has the best chance of achieving positive and equitable outcomes for nature and people.

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